

THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE SKILLS THROUGH SHADOWING EXERCISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8379476>

Annotation: With increasing interest in the communicative approach to English language teaching, many universities and high schools have started to teach shadowing in their language program. Shadowing is a standard exercise in training programs for interpreters, but shadowing has also a number of positive aspects for English language learners. This article scrutinizes how shadowing can contribute to the field of language learning by examining one English class where students practice shadowing.

Key words: English language, communicative approach, “Shadowing” technique, communicative competence, speaking skill, speech competence, communicative language teaching.

In this day and age, English has become an international language. It is spoken, learnt, and understood even in those countries in which it is not a native language. Many sectors including medicine, engineering, education, advanced studies, business, technology, banking, computing, tourism, and other fields all rely heavily on English (Kadamovna, 2021). The core content of this subject helps students form and develop communication skills through exposing listening, speaking reading, writing skills and language knowledge (phonetics, vocabulary, and grammar). The main focus of English in the new general education program is the communicative language teaching. This approach emphasizes the formation and development of students’ communication ability.

Communication methods share some similarities with the learner-centered approach in education. This mainstream regulates the teaching activities of teachers and the learning activities of students. It is undeniable that communication will not take place unless people can express the language to their partner. As a result, as years by, the role of speaking skill in English education has more emphasized than before. The importance of speaking effectively lies in its tremendous potential to induce change in language learning. Because of speaking, students can communicate with other students in our country or different countries to share ideas and opinions. Learning the speaking skill is the most important aspect of learning a second or foreign language and success is measured based on the ability to perform a conversation in the language (Nunan, 1995). Sharing the same notion, Ur (1996) lists speaking as one of the most important skills of all the four language skills because individuals who learn a language are referred to as the speakers of that language.

The basic purpose of English language instruction is to prepare pupils to speak effectively and properly in English. Language learners, on the other hand, seem to be unable to communicate easily and correctly as a result of a lack of comprehension in this area (Davies & Pearse, 2000). Many students claim that they have spent years learning English yet are still unable to speak it properly and clearly (Bueno, Madrid, & McLaren, 2006). For over 3 years, we have been teaching English as a foreign language to Uzbek students. Despite the fact that they, like many other students in their circumstances, can read and write rather well, they are victims of a conventional education that did not put a strong importance on listening and speaking

skills. To learn to speak, students must put in a lot of practice time. Teachers might model structures for their students and ask them to repeat them.

Shadowing method, also known as parody speech technique, was developed in the late 1950s under the term Shadowing Speech. This approach is widely regarded as one of the most successful methods in assisting students in developing all areas of speaking abilities, including Pronunciation, Prosody, and Rhythm. Simultaneously, this strategy assists learners in increasing their vocabulary, improving communication fluency, forming an impression of sentence patterns, and promoting autonomy in learning.

Several educational specialists have recently conducted studies on shadowing and its usefulness for foreign language acquisition in general and skills instructions in particular. However, many remains unclear regarding how to effectively assist language learners enhance their speaking abilities using the shadowing strategy. This study contributes to the research literature by filling gaps in the teaching practice of EFL and ESL speaking skills and revealing the effects of shadowing on students' speaking performance.

Speaking is one of the four macro skills necessary for effective communication in any language, particularly when speakers are not using their mother tongue. Speaking is a very important skills, it helps people in communication to be able to convey their meaning or message to others. Speaking is a macro language skill that is actively used to convey messages and meanings (Asakereh, 2016). It can be seen that speaking skill is a language related to communication. It means that speaking is the skill of using language appropriately to express someone's ideas, opinions or feelings in order to provide or obtain information and knowledge from others. In this current study, speaking is defined as the learner's ability to express himself/herself orally, coherently, fluently and appropriately in a given meaningful context.

Defined by Lambert (1992), shadowing entails a paced tracking of the heard speech in parrot style, the word-for-word repetition of a piece of information in one language, through the headphones. Originally, shadowing is a technique used by cognitive psychologists and neuropsychologists, and utilized as a method to improve simultaneous interpretation skills. However, Hamada (2011) argues that Lambert's (1992) definition does not encompass cognitive processes, a significant concept of shadowing. He claims that shadowing should be deemed as "an active and highly cognitive activity" rather than the auditory repetition. Jaramillo & Isaza (2016) describe shadowing as a method to train interpreters in Europe, and it is widely applied in Uzbekistan to improve English skills nowadays.

Seo & Takeuchi (n.d) shared the same opinion when it comes to the use of shadowing among the simultaneous interpreters. They stated that shadowing was originally regarded as a technique for training concurrent interpreters, but it is adapted in language classrooms by high school students and teachers. They believed that this practice enables learners to develop their mental resources and memorial abilities.

From the above definitions, we can define shadowing is an advanced learning technique where one listens to a text in your target language, and then speaks it aloud at the same time as the native speaker.

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